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Symbolic Interactionism as a Methodology for Process Organization Studies: Grounding the Enactment of Competences in Organizational Life

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Abstract

Management research often treats the competences within firms as 'fait accompli'. Process organization studies can tackle this challenge through focusing on how and why competences emerge. We propose that symbolical interactionism is a suitable process philosophical framework to explore the social organization immanent in the accomplishment of key organizational processes. Through drawing on ethnography and the construction of living stories, a reconstructive empirical study of an organization shows how role taking contributes to competences.

1. Introduction

'What we used to call organizations must now be imagined as mere moments of processes.' (Abbott, 2009: 22-23).

Research on critical success factors may lead to the belief that competitiveness and/or competitive advantages depend on factors, such as market share, product quality, price competitiveness, or customer loyalty (David, 2013). All of which are assumptions that have been questioned on several accounts (Nicolai & Kieser, 2002).

Both the resource-based view (Barney, 1991) and the dynamic capability/core competence perspective (Teece, 2007; Hamel & Prahalad, 1994), point at corporate resources and competences, suggesting that the roots of these performance indicators may lie *deeper* in terms of organizational structures. However, these perspectives often tackle *end-of-pipe* phenomena while neglecting early causal elements. The organizational phenomena, in question, demand an alignment of theory, perspective, and method that depart from mainstream approaches to research in traditional organization and management studies. Process organization studies have become a useful perspective to gain a deeper understanding why firms succeed or fail (Langley, 2007).

Competence-based theories argue that gains in productivity may follow from embedding a strategic mindset throughout the organization (Sanchez et al., 1996), therewith framing actors' awareness. Capturing the goings-on of organizations requires a methodological grasp for complexity, which is seldom offered (Tsoukas, 2017). This is where a process-based focus on interactions can help throw fresh light onto the becoming of an organization's competence, in which acquired cultural predispositions through *role taking* are crucial. Understanding competence as a set of established patterns of relations that actors take on through everyday life at work may explain phenomena that are often mind bugging to scholars. How can actors in the front-stage of the organization be routinely oriented towards seeking business opportunities, whereas behind the scenes, they are weary or disgruntled about the prospect of fresh opportunities? Although a processual perspective lies at the core of competence-based research, mundane real-world phenomena only gradually move into sight. We tackle this shortcoming by attending to calls for a stronger process orientation through exploring interactions within an organization, which also involves making processes tangible. Such work is likely to foster understanding of organizational life and the emergence of competence, a phenomenon that precedes pertinent issues in the field of management, such as the advent of (digital) transformation. In order to capture the complexity of transformations, a holistic understanding of organizational life is necessary. Organizational members use this very understanding, much like an underlying logic orienting action (Sandberg & Tsoukas, 2011) to enact competences. In addition, rigidity and other barriers to transformation demand examination. Although process organization studies have been praised for helping to increase our understanding of major events that impact

organizational outcomes, this perspective has often left unattended the majority of organizational accomplishments, which continually emerge from small-scale disturbances in everyday organizational life (Feldman, 2000; Turner & Rindova, 2012). Overall, this literature is poised towards efficiency, but neglects major phenomena that inhibit transformation, such as intra-firm conflicts (Pitelis, 2009). It appears as though the intricacies of social organization fly underneath the radar of competence-based management research.

Appreciating a process-inspired way of understanding organizational competence requires first a look at a process-philosophical approach towards analyzing organizations. The latter helps to understand the actions of actors, who embody organizational competence, before 'reconstructing the logic that explicates how and why these patterns occur [. . .]' (Wenzel/Koch 2018: 87, among others referring to Langley et al., 2013).

We argue that the theoretical frame of Symbolic Interactionism (SI) aids in researching competences by helping to understand the inherently processual nature of organizational life. SI is inspired by Mead (1932) among others, whose work has recently been dubbed as an important foundation to process philosophy (Simpson, 2009).

In the following section, the conceptual puzzle is first highlighted before treating the conceptual background for our study by laying out the methodological directives of SI (Blumer, 1969), which help understanding the social organization of within-firm processes (Dionysiou & Tsoukas, 2013). This study then considers *how* process from a symbolical interactionist perspective may be researched by laying down ethnography as a suitable methodology. After an account of the research process, ethnographic stories present the empirical material. This serves to create a story-based style of theorizing the process of competence *enactment*. Finally, the findings are discussed in a symbolical interactionist perspective on the social organization of organizational competence.

Conceptual puzzle

Process perspectives seek to advance a closer look at the within-firm structures (Sveningsson & Alvesson, 2003) in order to explain organizational outcomes (Samra-Fredericks, 2003; Crevani et al., 2010). Process organization studies of competences can support building an understanding of how firm-specific traits nurture competences

through every day goings-on (Chia & Holt, 2006; Whitford & Zirpoli, 2014). This concern demands grounding theory in specific competitive contexts, if competence research is to be both theoretically sound and helpful to the business domain (Mahoney & Sanchez, 2004).

This gave us the motivation to explain *how* (notice the process) competence is enacted within firms while considering its embodied nature. Process methodology in management research aids in focusing on the very emergence of social

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organization (Sminia, 2009) with the help of its focal construct *interaction* (Langley et al., 2013). Competence-based research inspired by the *acting men* notion (von Mises, 1949) states that within a firm everyone should have, at least, some discretion to act entrepreneurially (for an overview, see Freiling et al., 2008). Accordingly, the *discretion to act* needs to be understood within the local context of *social* organization. Competence research that restricts itself to an entitative view of action fails to grasp the dynamics underlying organizational life. In this article, we accept the challenge to specify '*micro-logics* of social organizing practices over and above their stabilized "effects", such as "individuals", "organizations", and "society"' (italics in original, Chia, 1995: 580). For this, we propose the application of *process-* theorizing that considers the meanings actors assign to their actions. A methodological framework capable of grasping these phenomena highlights the salience of human experience to social scientific endeavors. What is still unclear is how an improved understanding of interactions can explain the emergence of organizational competence. Our research question addresses this gap by asking: how do social organizing practices contribute to the enactment of organizational competence?

Symbolic interactionism as a process methodology

This article introduces symbolic interactionism to grasp the everyday goings-on in organizational life. A process-philosophical worldview sees social reality as the result of

ever evolving social construction (Chia & King, 1998). SI's methodology intends to tackle the emergent nature of social life; it grants importance to human experience and subjective knowledge. Classic texts in organization theory praise SI for its consistent theoretical and methodological basis, a true blueprint for ideographic studies of management (Burrell & Morgan, 1979). Yet, most SI studies of social organization have appeared in scholarly outlets outside of management research (McGinty, 2014).

In times during which organizations were conceptualized as ready-to-act entities (Pugh, 1981), SI already, clearly deviated from the abstractionist agenda of management studies. As attention shifts to consider how internal firm processes *become* organized to act (Chia, 1995), SI presents an intriguing alternative to entitative views of organizations. Here, SI provides a process-philosophical worldview that is best grounded on data through ethnographic research of process from within the organization. Stating that contextual factors and processes *fly underneath the radar* of competence-based research means to acknowledge blind spots that emanate from etic approaches to organizational processes. Critical academic engagement with management further highlights that these studies often privilege the perspective of power holders (Tatli & Özbilgin, 2012), therefore misrepresenting many bearers of organizational competence. By contrast, emic approaches that allow for the inclusion of disenfranchised voices provide space for additional perspectives. Such endeavors make management research more pluralistic and enrich the understanding of organizational processes. Drawing on Mead as a

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process philosopher and the corpus of symbolic interactionism as a process methodology, we *ground* the concept of role taking (Mead, 1932) on data. This serves to account for the uncertainty that individuals seek to overcome 'through noting and interpreting features of the situations in which he [/she] acts' (Blumer, 1969: 83). By extension, through an ethnographic methodology, we also capture the *situatedness* or context-specificity that is part of the accomplishment of an organizational competence in action. We propose that role taking within interactions is an important process through which competence is configured.

For Mead (1932: 165):

The human experience with which social science occupies itself is primarily that of

individuals. It is only so far as the happenings, the environmental conditions, the values, their uniformities and laws, *enter into the experience of individuals* as individuals that they become the subject of consideration by these sciences. Environmental conditions, for example, exist only in so far as they *affect actual individuals* and only as they affect these individuals. Furthermore, the import of these happenings and these values must be found in *the experience of these individuals* if they are to exist for these sciences at all. (own emphasis)

Sociological traditions continually influence management research, yet tensions resurface as different practices of knowledge validation abound. 'For sociology oriented to [sic!] empirical research concepts need to be grounded on data (whatever counts as data)' (Gherardi, 2016: 683). The process philosophical framing of SI has received some attention, but applications do not reflect this in their methodology. There is the example of Mead, whose work appears in the theoretical framing of many articles on process organization studies. The available work very seldom operationalizes Mead's core assumptions thoroughly (for further examples in different strands of social theory, see Gherardi, 2016: 683). Within pragmatist versions of process organization studies, those interested in interactions as empirical phenomena that trigger role taking can be distinguished from other studies that consider interactions as an epistemology (Dionysiou & Tsoukas, 2013).

To operationalize Mead's thinking coherently in management studies means moving from investigations of organizations from the outside (the etic perspective) to the inside (the emic perspective). As it stands, management research, which favors abstract descriptions of organizations, may be complemented by evidence of the lived experience (the qualia) of these organizations (Gärtner, 2013), thus drawing attention to the fact that organizations are *inhabited*. It builds on process philosophy that already implies symbolic interactionist thinking (Mead, 1932). In such an approach, the definition of a social situation provides guidelines for future social interactions; such definitions *construct* these interactions (Hallett & Ventresca, 2006). Organizations operate recursively (von Foerster, 2003); so the meanings of things are constructed and propelled forward by social interactions (Hallett &

Ventresca, 2006). Order and interaction bring about an *interaction order*. This interaction order features the likely definitions of reality as well as the consequences for actors who break with the prevalent definition of social reality (Fine, 1993). Essentially, this perspective engages in retrospective sensemaking of interactions that make up the social organization of the firm. Organizational competence may then be explained by the structuring effects of interactions, such that organizational phenomena can be built *up from the ground*.

Figure 1: Role taking originating in interactions (adapted from Dionysiou & Tsoukas, 2013).

Methodological Issue

Primary aim

Identity (researcher role)

Researcher-participant
relations

Representation

Organizational Ethnography

Authentic rich description of organizational cultural settings. Often

aimed at revealing unseen or marginal communities. The radical writer as autonomous artist.

Giving 'voice' to participants.

Empathetic accounts from the perspective of the participants.

Ideals of representing marginal or unheard voices through authorial interpretation and skilled writing (Van Maanen, 2011).

Power relations and ethics Critical reflexivity – sensitivity to power relations but remedy located less

Methodological tactics

in the field and more in how participants are represented in written text. Observation.

Participation.

Interview.

Critical reflexive thick description (Cunliffe, 2002).

Table 1: Procedural virtues of critical academic engagement (adapted from Reedy & King, 2017).

Figure 1 illustrates the construction of social reality, to help understand how actors enact competence through the performative process of role taking. Social reality becomes established through *taking the role of the other*; this process of anticipating the actions of others explains social organization (Blumer, 1969) and is initiated through interactions. Competence theory considers actors to possess subjective minds (Freiling et al., 2008). These are the individual understandings (subjectivism) of actors that role taking aligns with those of other actors whose actions affect them in a considerable way (Mead, 1932) (see fig. 1). The process model assumes that

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participants initiate interactions in a specific context when they have an initial orientation toward a joint activity and some uncertainty. Joint situated understandings develop as an outcome of interactions. "We "are" what they expect if we communicate recognition of the situation' (Altheide, 2000: 4). Therefore, it is of particular interest what the role expectations of others mean for actors. Recurrent interactional patterns are considered a plausible indication of the prevailing social organization of a context. The *situatedness* of understandings stems from its embeddedness in a context of interaction (Elsbach et al., 2005; Lave & Wenger, 1991). From these understandings, individuals may act intuitively or use expectations from prior encounters to guide their actions (Fiske & Taylor, 1991). This stream of research promises to bring organizational life to the forefront to help gain greater insight into how micro-logics within organizations shape organizational action.

Metaphors and narratives come into being in and through enacting discursive (and other social) practices, which evolve in a situated context of interaction. The metaphors that individuals express for all practical purposes are meaningful empirical illustrations of sensemaking that are shaped within organizations (Maitlis & Christianson, 2014).

SI implies a corresponding method, which Blumer (1969) sought to explicate through naturalistic inquiry (Athens, 2010), providing the means to account for role taking coherently. The ideographic method depicts an interaction order by means of narrative, i.e. a story, the ethnographic text. Apart from work that explicitly embraces Mead's philosophy, SI has had an enormous impact on ethnographic practice (e.g. Spradley, 1980). Ethnography involves fieldwork, headwork and textwork (Van Maanen, 2011). Irrespective of theoretical framing, the fieldwork involved in ethnography is among those approaches considered suitable to capture data on organizational processes (Langley et al., 2013). Empirically researching processes that build up higher-level phenomena and outcomes, like organizational competence, requires longitudinal, rich, and varied data (Langley et al., 2013). In process organization studies, ethnography has recently been embraced because it conventionally involves analyzing life worlds that evolve over time while capturing recollections, metaphors, and stories abounding in organizational practices (Langley et al., 2013). A process perspective grounded in SI benefits from the headwork (Van Maanen, 2011) involved in ethnography, grounding our explanations in situated interactions (Dionysiou & Tsoukas, 2013) of actors' lived experiences. The thick description that ethnography and interpretive research have become associated with in management studies (Cornelissen, 2017) is the textwork placing emphasis on written accounts and metaphors. It may be considered a story-based style of theorizing process (Pentland, 1999).

Ethnographic texts that conventionally take the form of scholarly monographs are known for telling tales of a situated context, which are essentially made up of smaller stories capturing the researcher's experience or that of informants. Ethnographic

research captures participants' everyday sensemaking and illuminates the contextual factors of

process. To situate our methodological discussion of ethnographic textwork, we build on Rosile, Boje, Carlon, Downs and Saylor (2013) to mediate between the more abstract competence-based literature and the stories that stem from sensemaking of organizational members. Both competence-based literature, as well as the stories colleagues exchange in copy rooms or over lunch, are relevant for understanding organizational processes. But how is that? Picture yourself within a company, participating and listening to the stories informants share with you. Sometimes the information gleaned from the research sites is irritating; it simply is not in line with competence-based reasoning, begging the question 'What's the story? Now what?' (Weick, 2009: 195).

Most of management research engages in methodological procedures that bracket (Giddens, 1984) contextual influences on organizational process. Giddens (1984: 285), among others, cautions researchers not to mistake these methodological moves for an 'ontological reality'. However, this invariably occurs when researchers take an etic approach as a neutral observer to studying organizations. This abstract type of inquiry focuses on the extraction of elements from informants' stories (see e.g., Bluhm et al., 2011), with the objective to reveal 'generalizable facts and claims to truth' (Rosile et al., 2013: 563). A recent example of qualitative research that hints at a common agenda of methodology and theorizing that is shared with quantitative research (Cornelissen, 2017) is the so-called 'Gioia methodology' (Gioia et al., 2013). Yet, such abstractionist research often struggles with many research questions inspired by real-world problems (Rosile et al., 2013: 563). We argue that this particularly holds for process organization studies conducted from outside the organization. By contrast, an emic methodological alternative, that provides an understanding of an experienced truth of 'Being-in-the-world' (Rosile et al., 2013: 564), may capture the situatedness of idiosyncratic settings, as they matter for processes leading to organizational competences. Through focusing on the intricacies of social life in *situ*, we do not mean to downplay 'abstracting to the universalist or transcendent level of knowing' (Rosile et al., 2013: 566). Analytic approaches to ethnography (e.g., Snow et al., 2003) and content analysis (Bluhm et al., 2011) matter, but we have made the analytical choice to focus on thick description here. The aim to contribute a process understanding of the enactment of competences motivates this choice. Such research takes subjectivism seriously, since it also acknowledges variety in actors' awareness. For example, top-down decisions can prompt sensemaking that triggers resistance to the alignment of understandings among actors (Sonenshein, 2010). We show how process research that adopts ethnographic methodologies generates living stories to provide greater depth of understanding. *Living*, refers to transporting the lived experience generated by ethnography with all its ambiguities into text. The living stories of one group,

e.g. the clerks may help to understand another group, e.g. top or middle management (Rosile et al., 2013: 570).

Earlier advances of SI in process organization studies, e.g. (Dionysiou & Tsoukas, JCSM, Vol. 10: 139-161

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2013) provide insightful conceptualizations even though researchers pursued an abstractionist approach. To refocus theory on social reality within organizations (Mahoney & Sanchez, 2004), it is necessary to ground agency in the relational experience of actors. Given the space limits of a journal article, ethnographic textwork uses vignettes as shorter episodes of thick description (Van Maanen, 2011). Vignettes are a suitable means to provide empathetic accounts from the perspective of actors, since they reveal participants' affects (Ripamonti et al., 2016). The vignettes focus on interactional issues related to the enactment of competence in this organizational setting. Table 1 summarizes procedural virtues for ethnography that aid in characterizing our stance towards critical academic engagement.

2. The research process

This article is based on a broader in-depth ethnographic study of *The Warehouse* (TW, a pseudonym), conducted over a 6-month period as a complete member-researcher by one of the authors. The study relies on longitudinal real-time ethnographic data to observe how processes unfold over time (Langley et al., 2013: 6). Increasingly, qualitative researchers are expected to acquire *interactional expertise* (Collins, 2004) as a form of knowledge that allows them to meaningfully engage with informants, subject matter, and context. Ethnographic research inspired by SI also refers to such expertise as firsthand knowledge of the empirical problem under study (Athens, 2010). One of the authors already had several years of work experience as a clerk in trading and warehousing before fieldwork began. These advanced practitioner skills are important for understanding highly specialized organizing practices (see also Bruns, 2013). The purpose of the research was to explore social organizing practices that contribute to organizational competence in a competitive setting. This is indicated by calls to make strategy research more relevant to management practice (Mahoney & Sanchez, 2004; Ripamonti et al., 2016).

Access to the research site was granted based on one researcher's organizational role as an office floor clerk, which brought an immersion into the day-to-day business with it. The researcher

worked among commercial clerks in office headquarters and took hand-written notes of descriptive, focused, and selective observations (Spradley, 1980). The research project evolved from mainly descriptive and focused observations to more selective observations towards the close of the study. The rough observational notes were supplemented by further analytical, theoretical, and methodological notes (Schatzman & Strauss, 1973). The methodological notes treat practicalities of research organization. The theoretical notes capture aspects of observation that relate to prior known sensitizing concepts while the analytical notes capture researcher ideas in the sense of emergent abductive suggestions (Timmermans & Tavory, 2012). In research practice, subjective experiences and affects are also recorded as analytical notes, thus providing even richer data. Through interacting with 17 informants (office floor personnel and middle managers) and hosting informal interviews of 30 to 45 minutes, over 120 field notes (average: 2-5

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pages) were generated.

Based on the methodological directives of SI, the overarching rationale that guided the data analysis was to inquire the meaning arising out of the interaction among participants with a social situation (Blumer, 1969). The empirical material was then analyzed to find recurring patterns allowing to prepare both thick *and* pattern descriptions to grasp the meaning by which actors act. Such a semantic explanatory programme contains both concrete and abstract aspects of theorizing process (Cornelissen, 2017, drawing on Abbott, 2004). 'The semantic [explanatory] programme explains particulars by assimilating it to more and more general patterns, searching for regularities over time or across settings' (Cornelissen, 2017: 372).

As many cultural meanings remain tacit, research has generated analytical domains from what people in the social scene do and say (Spradley, 1980: 91). Interaction patterns were explicated subsequently through applying the method of constant comparison (Schatzman & Strauss, 1973). Comparisons across multiple observations and notes were made to form conceptual generalizations about interactions (Tsoukas, 1989). In this article we refer only to two domains, one is the *wise men* domain (a folk term and an expression actually used by people in the social setting) and the other is the analytical term, *the experienced* (generated through research). The steps involved in a domain analysis are briefly described below.

A domain analysis (Spradley, 1980) has served to establish semantic links between analytical notes. The semantic relationships, *X is a kind of Y* and *X is a way to Y*, were applied to further grasp the patterns of meaning abounding in this cultural scene. The semantic relationship of a strict inclusion is expressed by, *X is a kind of Y*. If the relation is applied to the distribution of power within the organization, the relationship may be expressed as the following, *the experienced actor is a kind of father*. The semantic relationship of a means-end relation is expressed by, *X is a way to Y* can be applied to the rituals and expressed as such, *watching football together is a corporate form of socialization*.

By comparing the analytical notes, it became apparent that in most interactions the definition of the situation and role taking is an issue. In this way, *how* actors define the situation involving social interaction with others across several interactions is essential. Building on methodological recommendations for ethnographic textwork (Spradley, 1980: 140), a storied account of the research site's social organization was reconstructed from the empirical material. Such moves are encouraged by calls to provide a stronger impetus to rethink conventional wisdom in management research (Alvesson & Sandberg, 2013), as well as calls for process inspired theorizing (Wenzel & Koch, 2018).

As mentioned above, the cultural domain of *wise men* emerged from the analysis and became the analytical focus of the ethnography because it organizes most of the cultural meaning of this scene. An ethnographic focus emerges when a particular

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domain can be seen to tie together all of the information relevant to an empirical problem (Spradley, 1980: 106). In this article, the reconstruction of the theme *wise men* is presented, concentrating on actors' sensemaking and plausible consequences of interactions. Through detailing how employees experience and make sense of interaction patterns, attention is drawn towards the relational qualities of agency.

The trustworthiness of empirical fieldwork was realized through carrying out the steps recommended for a naturalistic inquiry (Guba, 1981): prolonged presence within the research context, continuous participant observation, triangulation of findings through the method of constant comparison, and debriefing with fellow researchers and examination of

conflicting cases. Naturalistic Inquiry is an approach commensurable both to SI and ethnography. The replicability criterion is established by providing a richly contextualized account of the research site (Guba, 1981).

3. A symbolical interactionist approach to the social organization of competence

A: "Can I give Stein a quick call? He's in warehouse 3."

B: "No, that's not possible we have removed all telephones out there."

A: "Now what's the point in that?!"

B: "Wise men have decided thus " ('weise Männer haben das entschieden')
(Excerpt from the field notes, authors' translation)

In the following sections, we use the case of *The Warehouse* (TW) to explore how role taking, a social organizing practice, shapes how actors enact competence. First, how truth is determined in marketplace action is discussed. Second, the complex interactions that provide actors with a grasp of social reality within the firm is explored through vignettes. Then in the last section of the article, the focus is drawn towards the social organization as structured through interactions and its drawback for the emergence of organizational competence. From this point onwards, this article will follow a social-constructionist approach to social science in which 'empirical research is essentially a form of "story-telling" (Astley & Zammuto, 1992: 449, citing Daft, 1983).

Organizational competence of *The Warehouse*

120 people are engaged in commercial trading and warehousing at TW headquarters. Globally, it employs approximately 500 staff in 10 branches. It is a second-generation family-run business, which could be termed a hidden champion for specialty metals. The distinctive organizational competence of TW is defined by its ability to provide a special service. TW solves the problem of matching customers' demand for goods and producers' to readily available manufactured goods. The products of hundreds of producers are distributed across the globe based on individual sales orders. The sales department is the most visible and powerful subculture at the organizational level. This functional subculture and its share in

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shaping the organizational competence lies at the center of attention. In the following sections, the case material is used to explore how social organizing practices contribute to the enactment of organizational competence.

Truth as that which works, the purely pragmatic criterion

TW's strategic mindset fostered within market transactions displays traits akin to the nature of entrepreneurial activity, epitomized through the metaphor *nothing is impossible* ('geht nicht, gibts nicht'). At TW a pragmatic definition of the situation applies to market transactions; truth is defined according to *physical* reality. If external knowledge may help to win over a client or realize an important sales order, then it does not matter whether it breaks with traditional ways of knowledge search.

Booking a sales order and entering it into the warehousing system rewards the actor who displays a high degree of activity. In this competitive environment, success is displayed through securing sales orders with clients, and in turn securing a supplier whose offer matches client requirements. The facts that matter for sales people are to make enough profit allowing their organization to stay in the competition. After looking at how competence is socially constructed through market interactions, we now turn towards social reality as it pertains to the internal realm of the firm. Thus far, we have shown that acting entrepreneurially comes as actors' *second nature*. The sensemaking fostered in the realm of market action rewards the discretion to act in an entrepreneurial manner.

Vignette 1: Breach of rules

Operation nostechradzor was instigated by Mr. Gomel, the head of the plant, in response to the upcoming expiration of the contract with the foreign classification agency. The warehouse depended on the continuous approval of this agency to be allowed to compete on foreign markets. Mr. Gomel considered what might be done to ensure that the inspection would run smoothly. He conferred with the head of the sales department and asked if a senior sales manager, Mr. Teun, could be sent in to assist with the inspection at the plant, as he possesses a relevant foreign language proficiency. As Mr. Teun is an expert in this market, the head of sales agreed to let him join the external surveyor to carry out the inspection of the plant.

A couple of days after the successful inspection, Mr. Teun received a call from the head of the technical department, Mr. Zed. Mr. Zed is incensed at the fact that his authority had been omitted from the decision-making process. As a result, Mr. Zed accused Mr. Teun of deceiving him personally as well as the technical department. He was accused of having gone too far in stretching his discretion to act. For any business related to third-party inspections, Mr. Zed and the technical department strictly bear the sole responsibility. Mr. Teun accepted his reprimanding, although he had only followed his intuition by regarding the inspection as a natural extension of his everyday mission to satisfy customer needs.

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This illustrated incident helps to answer our research question. *Taking the role of the other* during the passage of *interaction* (see fig. 1) drives actors to align their actions with the role of wise men, rather than acting upon an entrepreneurial *gut feeling*. Interactions therefore account for a social organization that constrains the enactment of competence. This finding conflicts with the hard-core assumption of competence-based research: the notion of acting men. The creation of joint understandings in the passage, illustrated in figure 1 by the vertical arrow marked with an *e*, ensures the alignment of understandings and actions. Sales managers utilize this joint understanding to enact the social order of wise men. The vignette serves as an example of how actors gain experience about the meanings of their actions, which they can then use for future interactions.

The process perspective of SI helps to improve our understanding of how the acting men notion becomes enacted in organizational life. The construct of role taking draws attention to the relevant other of interaction partners (Mead, 1934). When Mr. Zed enters the scene of the sales department to reproach Mr. Teun, he offers a definition of the situation that strongly irritates the sensibility prevalent in the sales group. In the SI thinking, the interaction serves to make the *generalized other* sensible. This holds for Mr. Teun and for any sales manager for that matter. With this lens, enacting competences is no longer an abstract possibility, but tangible as a string of interactions among organizational members. Such interactions generate sensemaking for future actions (asking *how* do I go on? while enacting organizational competence). Mr. Teun gained experience, allowing him 'to approach oneself from the position of an abstract: "they", standing in some form of organized relationship to one' (Blumer, 2004: 61). The social organization within which the sales team is situated influences the

experience of individual members through anticipating the generalized other. Not only the immediate sales supervisors carry out control over Mr. Teun, after all, they had given him the license to conduct the inspection. Also, other corporate functions exercise control over the sales team's discretion to act. Enacting competences is intimately tied to professional identity, which develops as individuals interact. From this follows that SI provides the key to a deeper understanding of organizational processes as they matter to key organizational outcomes.

Vignette 2: Then, you would be sitting in my place

Peter and Michaela exchange their views on the first appraisal interview that they recently had with their supervisor (or, rather, the head of department held an interview with them). [Author's note: *Emphasis is placed on the initiator of the interview.*] A close examination may confirm this.

Peter: "Were you satisfied with your appraisal interview?"

Michaela: "Oh well, so-so. The conversation actually went along quite positively, and he continuously praised me and didn't say a single negative word. However, in the final evaluation, it wasn't all positive."

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Peter: "You were classified as mediocre?"

Michaela: "Yes, exactly. With Brenda, it was quite similar, and then she asked why she only got a mediocre score, even though everything said was singly positive. John then replied, if she would get full marks in all areas, 'Then, you would be sitting in my place!'"

Peter: "That doesn't convince me."

Michaela: "Me neither."

[. . .]

Theoretical Note: the line managers were trained to conduct the appraisal interview [It is the first cycle of appraisal interviews that the company has run]. Presumably, there is still an air of tentativeness surrounding the appraisal interview. What consequences may accrue from such appraisal? A bad appraisal may burden the relationship between employee and supervisor. In the case of a markedly positive appraisal and classification, an employee could infer claims to a better wage or improved working conditions.

Due to the novelty of the appraisal interview, there is still an apprehension that employees may obtain sufficient evidence to make claims and put line managers into an inconvenient position. [...]

The appraisal interview is the creation of management to sustain the success of the corporation and to expand upon it. The employees should be supported in their personal development for the sake of the corporation's success. Thus far, the range of career advancement opportunities has concentrated on English language courses.

(excerpt from the fieldnotes, authors' translation)

At TW, the skills, potential skills, and skill deficiencies of the employees were to be systematically assessed and managed. The company eventually began to introduce measures that were directed at building up a human resource management system. In this context, a new vocabulary of personal growth and development was introduced. This concept on its own appeared to be a favorable trend for all employees.

A structured performance appraisal was to provide employees with feedback. The area of personnel development was to receive a more systematic treatment than what it had been previously given. Management recognized that employees had scarce access to the opinions or evaluations of their supervisors; it was simply something that was not officially discussed. Participation in a structured feedback-interview offered employees the opportunity to receive a detailed explanation of the role expectations of their supervisors. Management declared that through this formalized interaction, the employees and supervisors would be able to achieve a desirable level of open communication.

Management presented the initiative as a win-win-situation for both employees and supervisors. Members of the management team indicated that 'if someone is rated in

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stage 4, i.e., if a performance is higher than expected in the respective position, then this has to be accommodated for' (excerpt from field notes). Employees would learn of the opinions their supervisors hold about their performance and learn about their potential for development. The narrative that management foreshadowed before the interview raised expectations about personal growth and development; yet, there was some uncertainty about what

would result from getting full marks for performance. The concrete events at TW almost ironically mirror role taking in Mead's process philosophy, providing actors the opportunity to approach themselves from the position of an abstract 'they' standing in front of them, like in the first vignette. The role taking that unfolds in vignette 2 shows how expectations about personal growth and development are managed. Although management narratives indicated that they would acknowledge proper performance, the reviewed employees were neither given criticism, nor advised on how to improve their performance. Resultantly, the team members were left irritated.

4. Discussion: what a symbolic interactionist approach to social organization contributes to research on organizational competence

We began by asking how it might be possible to combine research on organizational competences with a process philosophical perspective that draws attention to everyday social organizing practices. In figure 1, we show the pattern description that up until now was used only as an epistemology of process organization studies (Dionysiou & Tsoukas, 2013). Table 1 shows the methodological directives of SI that were followed through our engagement with the research setting to actually ground the social theoretical patterns of interactions in empirical material. We contributed living stories from ethnographic fieldwork that allude to the semantic explanatory programs of both thick and pattern descriptions (Cornelissen, 2017). Finally, the methodological directives of SI and our take on process theorizing are offered as an initial point for competence researchers to reflect on the challenges of 'path-(up)setting scholarship mode' (Alvesson & Sandberg, 2013: 148).

Enacting organizational competence is an effortful accomplishment that has not often been grounded in the everyday of actors. Particularly, the mundane events matter for the emergence of competence. Abstractionist research paradigms have been rather successful in shielding their data generation procedures from the human experience of organizational life. This is even more surprising given the heightened interest in processual perspectives of phenomena, such as the emergence of organizational competence.

Storytelling of human experience generated through SI inquiry explains actors' identity and rationality. Both are deeply entwined with the competitive context as the vignettes show. Mead's process-relational concept of *taking the role of the other* helps to understand actors' conduct. By ignoring the competitive context and within- firm dynamics, no understanding of social organization may ensue. In the first vignette, the interactions after Mr.

Teun's mission led to a sanction, which guided

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awareness for future action. To account for the social order, as that of wise men, is to question the view of agency present in competence-based research. It is the opposite of the pragmatic criterion for defining a situation found within market interactions.

Interactions are ubiquitous and reduce uncertainty for actors; therefore, they deserve proper attention in process organization studies. The living stories that researchers can generate through SI help to understand the emergent order that actors infer from events and encounters *in situ* and that contribute to organizational outcomes. Considering temporality and historicity of organizational processes, asking *what was before?* and *what follows after?*, provides opportunities for accounts of social reality, putting forth the inclusion of diverse perspectives serving to offer a more holistic understanding of organizations (see also, Weick et al., 2005). By providing deep descriptions, accounts of rationality may be evaluated against the criterion of plausibility. Etic approaches to organizational stories fade out non-elite voices so that they obstruct truly understanding barriers to transformations.

At TW, actors are experts in their own right, as far as marketplace interactions are concerned. Within-firm organizational interactions do not follow a *negotiated* social order (Fine, 1984) in which there is a level playing field for every actor to define social reality, but instead there is an insistence upon subordination. The roles cultivated within the firm become real to the degree that they enter actors' experience as real. The role taking actors carry out accounts for the enactment of competence and lets the sales manager reconsider future actions. In this way, the within-firm interactions shape awareness of actors. The sales managers who enact organizational competence will do so in a considerably narrow sense of task work, which ensures playing according to the rules of the social situation. This is another outcome of enacting competences bearing in mind that one's discretion to act is limited by the definition of the situation of others in the immediate work environment (vignette 2), and also in the organization, at large (vignette 1). Therefore, the interactions that determine social reality affect the nature of enacting competences within the sales team. *How* salespeople will strive for their firm's competitiveness may be explained through living stories generated through SI.

We contribute semantic explanations (Cornelissen, 2017) that allow the reader to participate in the actions described (Stablein & North, 1985; Watson, 2011; Willmott, 1997). Through this level of detailed description, we enable readers to go through naturalistic

generalizations (Stake & Trumbull, 1982). It should be possible for the reader to relate to previously known or self-experienced events through the described social situations. Providing a detailed contextually rich account of the enactment of organizational competence is meant to stimulate further reflection with the reader (Stake, 1995: 42). The reader's reflections are often based on personal experiences. Stake and Trumbull (1982) refer to this *experiential learning* as naturalistic generalizations. Narrative descriptions form representative experiences for the reader (see Collins, 2010: 237). Assertions and naturalistic generalizations

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may be the source of existing initial presumptions about phenomena to be investigated, or they may promote their modification (Stake, 1995: 86).

The effects of interactions can sometimes be limiting and become palpable as they enter the experience of actors. Overall, it implies extinguishing the wholehearted entrepreneurial fire (Mainemelis, 2010) of a group that clearly displays the capability to act entrepreneurially. The case of TW has shown that the social organizing practices, that pervade within-firm interaction and provide meanings of social reality, exist side-by-side to market-oriented sensemaking of actors. Inspired by SI process philosophy the emic perspective uses living stories from the organization unearthing the notion of wise men, a metaphor that captures the social organization of striving for competitiveness and enacting competences in this context. It helps to understand how the interaction order, that carries a definition of social reality and foreshadows sanctions for deviant actors, constitutes barriers to transformation. The generative mechanisms of the situated interaction order curb rationality of actors through defining the situation as one with a considerable limitation of the discretion

to act.

Varying definitions of the situation

To summarize, the vignettes show how participants (informants and researchers) try to make sense around events and how sales managers make sense of what to do and who they are in relation to others. Here, the contestation of stories is constantly at issue. Identities are contested as Mr. Teun receives a telling off. Although we do not get the whole story, but only a fragment, we can imagine how frustrated Mr. Teun must feel. We see an illustration of how organizational members contest plausibility and simply do not buy into management narrative. This is also seen

in vignette 2. In the appraisal interview, the supervisor presents team members with a role that they contest. These living stories from the heart of organizational life are meant to be evocative and draw attention to underexposed, yet salient, aspects of organizational processes.

As researchers, we seek to organize the lived experience in alignment with the broader narrative of competence theory. We exemplified this through targeting its hard-core assumptions, the acting men notion (Freiling et al., 2008). The methodological contribution of this article coherently elaborates figure 1 through an empirical account that is capable to capture the joint understandings necessary to bring about aligned action.

With regard to the advent of digital transformation, storytelling researchers caution us 'to be aware of dominating stories presenting a univocal view, for while such stories may imbue order, they may limit other ways of making sense and acting' (Cunliffe & Coupland, 2012: 81). It can hardly be assumed that shared plots are neutral (Rhodes et al., 2010), as the vignettes show narrators respond almost initially to the role expectations that interaction partners (the generalized others) direct at

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them. SI helps to see these expectations because it draws attention to the organizational experience, which SI, as an epistemology, fails to account for.

5. Concluding Thoughts

In the article, we explain how actors enact competences through making sense of organizational context and experiences. We argue that living stories are useful to capture marginalized voices. Starting from the philosophical base assumptions of SI, which merit human experience, we highlight that the competence construct, which relies on actors' subjectivism, benefits from emic approaches to organizational process. This grants a more holistic understanding of identities and rationalities. Constructs from SI draw attention to the processual nature of organizations. This methodological contribution provides a counterpoint to the more abstract and taken for granted *entrepreneurial* nature of acting men.

By extension, also as researchers, we exhibit narrative performances of a struggle to work out which script applies. This discursive procedure of mediating between competences (as narrative) and the narratives of informants (as organizational stories) creates meaning

from many fragmented accounts of action. Our findings suggest that competence research may be conceptually aligned with SI. Therefore, it is a coherent way to expand process organization studies while accounting for the intricacies of social organization.

From the perspective of abstractionist etic approaches to sensemaking, ethnographic research as complete-member researchers (Brannick & Coghlan, 2007) is not problem-free, for example, explicit interferences from the investigator, difficulties with replication (Adler & Adler, 1987; Alvesson, 2003), and emotional involvement of the researcher (Maitlis et al., 2013; Rafaeli, 2013). The limitations of our theorizing and analysis through stories conflict with the understandable wish of the research community for abstracted categories. Given that we crossed somewhat uncharted territory, we suggest that future work should be done to align the living stories of our data with a more common etic approach to storytelling. A compromise between etic and emic accounts of organizational life is made through attempting to turn the deep descriptions of living story into abstracted categories (Rosile et al., 2013: 570).

References

- Abbott, A. (2009). Organizations and the Chicago School. In P. S. Adler (Ed.), *Oxford handbook of sociology and organization studies: Classical foundations*. Oxford University Press. Retrieved November 11, 2018, from <http://www.oxfordhandbooks.com/view/10.1093/oxfordhb/9780199535231.001.0001/oxfordhb-9780199535231-e-018>
- Abbott, A. (2004). *Methods of discovery: Heuristics for the social sciences*. W. W. Norton.
- Adler, P. A., & Adler, P. (1987). *Membership roles in field research* (Vol. 6). Sage.
- Altheide, D. L. (2000). Identity and the definition of the situation in a mass-mediated context. *Symbolic Interaction*, 23(1), 1–27.
- Alvesson, M. (2003). Methodology for close-up studies: Struggling with closeness and closure. *Higher Education*, 46(2), 167–193.
- Alvesson, M., & Sandberg, J. (2013). Has management studies lost its way? Ideas for more imaginative and innovative research. *Journal of Management Studies*, 50(1), 128–152.
- Astley, W. G., & Zammuto, R. F. (1992). Organization science, managers, and language games. *Organization Science*, 3(4), 443–460.

- Athens, L. (2010). Naturalistic inquiry in theory and practice. *Journal of Contemporary Ethnography*, 39(1), 87–125.
- Barney, J. (1991). Firm resources and sustained competitive advantage. *Journal of Management*, 17(1), 99–120.
- Brannick, T., & Coghlan, D. (2007). In defense of being “native”: The case for insider academic research. *Organizational Research Methods*, 10(1), 59–74.
- Bluhm, D. J., Harman, W., Lee, T. W., & Mitchell, T. R. (2011). Qualitative research in management: A decade of progress. *Journal of Management Studies*, 48(8), 1866–1891.
- Blumer, H. (1969). *Symbolic interactionism: Perspective and method*. Prentice Hall.
- Blumer, H. (2004). *George Herbert Mead and human conduct*. AltaMira Press.
- Burrell, G., & Morgan, G. (1979). *Sociological paradigms and organisational analysis: Elements of the sociology of corporate life*. Heinemann.
- Bruns, H. C. (2013). Working alone together: Coordination in collaboration across domains of expertise. *Academy of Management Journal*, 56(1), 62–83.
- Chia, R. (1995). From modern to postmodern organizational analysis. *Organization Studies*, 16(4), 579–604.
- Chia, R., & Holt, R. (2006). Strategy as practical coping: A Heideggerian perspective. *Organization Studies*, 27(5), 635–655.
- Chia, R., & King, I. W. (1998). The organizational structuring of novelty. *Organization*, 5(4), 461–478.
- Collins, H. (2004). Interactional expertise as a third kind of knowledge. *Phenomenology and the Cognitive Sciences*, 3(2), 125–143.
- Collins, P. (2010). The ethnographic self as resource? In P. Collins & A. Gallinat (Eds.), *The ethnographic self as resource: Writing memory and experience into ethnography* (pp. 228–245). Berghahn Books.
- Cornelissen, J. P. (2017). Preserving theoretical divergence in management research: Why the explanatory potential of qualitative research should be harnessed rather than suppressed. *Journal of Management Studies*, 54(3), 368–383.

Crevani, L., Lindgren, M., & Packendorff, J. (2010). Leadership, not leaders: On the study of leadership as practices and interactions. *Scandinavian Journal of Management*, 26(1), 77–86.

Cunliffe, A., & Coupland, C. (2012). From hero to villain to hero: Making experience sensible through embodied narrative sensemaking. *Human Relations*, 65(1), 63–88.

Cunliffe, A. L. (2002). Social poetics as management inquiry: A dialogical approach. *Journal of Management Inquiry*, 11(2), 128–146.

Daft, R. L. (1983). Learning the craft of organizational research. *Academy of Management Review*, 8(4), 539–546. <https://doi.org/10.5465/amr.1983.4284649>

Dionysiou, D. D., & Tsoukas, H. (2013). Understanding the (re)creation of routines from within: A symbolic interactionist perspective. *Academy of Management Review*, 38(2), 181–205.

ResearchGate Publication List (continued)

Elsbach, K. D., Barr, P. S., & Hargadon, A. B. (2005). Identifying situated cognition in organizations. *Organization Science*, 16(4), 422–433.

Feldman, M. S. (2000). Organizational routines as a source of continuous change. *Organization Science*, 11(6), 611–629.

Feldman, M. S., & Pentland, B. T. (2003). Reconceptualizing organizational routines as a source of flexibility and change. *Administrative Science Quarterly*, 48(1), 94–118.

Fine, G. A. (1984). Negotiated orders and organizational cultures. *Annual Review of Sociology*, 10(1), 239–262.

Fine, G. A. (1993). The sad demise, mysterious disappearance, and glorious triumph of symbolic interactionism. *Annual Review of Sociology*, 19(1), 61–87.

Fiske, S. T., & Taylor, S. E. (1991). *Social cognition* (2nd ed.). McGraw-Hill.

Freiling, J., Gersch, M., & Goeke, C. (2008). On the path towards a competence-based theory of the firm. *Organization Studies*, 29(8–9), 1143–1164.

Gärtner, C. (2013). Cognition, knowing and learning in the flesh: Six views on embodied knowing in organization studies. *Scandinavian Journal of Management*, 29(4), 338–352.

Gherardi, S. (2016). To start practice theorizing anew: The contribution of the concepts of agencement and formativeness. *Organization*, 23(5), 680–698.

Giddens, A. (1984). *The constitution of society: Outline of the theory of structuration*. University of California Press.

Gioia, D. A., Corley, K. G., & Hamilton, A. L. (2013). Seeking qualitative rigor in inductive research: Notes on the Gioia methodology. *Organizational Research Methods*, 16(1), 15–31.

Guba, E. G. (1981). Criteria for assessing the trustworthiness of naturalistic inquiries. *Educational Communication and Technology*, 29(2), 75–91.

Prahalad, C. K., & Hamel, G. (1994). Strategy as a field of study: Why search for a new paradigm? *Strategic Management Journal*, 15(S2), 5–16.

Pugh, D. S. (1981). The Aston Program perspective. In E. L. Trist, A. H. Van de Ven, & W. Joyce (Eds.), *Perspectives on organization design and behavior* (pp. 135–166). John Wiley & Sons.

Hallett, T., & Ventresca, M. J. (2006). How institutions form: Loose coupling as mechanism in Gouldner's patterns of industrial bureaucracy. *American Behavioral Scientist*, 49(7), 908–924.

Langley, A. (2007). Process thinking in strategic organization. *Strategic Organization*, 5(3), 271–282.

Langley, A., Smallman, C., & Tsoukas, H. (2013). Process studies of change in organization and management: Unveiling temporality, activity, and flow. *Academy of Management Journal*, 56(1), 1–13.

Lave, J., & Wenger, E. (1991). *Situated learning: Legitimate peripheral participation*. Cambridge University Press.

Mahoney, J. T., & Sanchez, R. (2004). Building new management theory by integrating processes and products of thought. *Journal of Management Inquiry*, 13(1), 34–47.

Mainemelis, C. (2010). Stealing fire: Creative deviance in the evolution of new ideas. *Academy of Management Review*, 35(4), 558–578.

Maitlis, S., & Christianson, M. (2014). Sensemaking in organizations: Taking stock and moving forward. *Academy of Management Annals*, 8(1), 57–125.

Maitlis, S., Vogus, T. J., & Lawrence, T. B. (2013). Sensemaking and emotion in organizations. *Organizational Psychology Review*, 3(3), 222–247.

McGinty, P. J. W. (2014). Divided and drifting: Interactionism and the neglect of social organizational analyses in organization studies. *Symbolic Interaction*, 37(2), 155–186.

- Mead, G. H. (1932). *The philosophy of the present*. The Open Court Company.
- Nicolai, A., & Kieser, A. (2002). Trotz eklatanter Erfolglosigkeit: Die Erfolgsfaktorenforschung weiter auf Erfolgskurs. *Die Betriebswirtschaft*, 62(6), 579–596.
- Pentland, B. T. (1999). Building process theory with narrative: From description to explanation. *Academy of Management Review*, 24(4), 711–724.
- Pitelis, C. N. (2009). Edith Penrose's *The theory of the growth of the firm* fifty years later. In E. T. Penrose, *The theory of the growth of the firm* (4th ed., pp. ix–xlvii). Oxford University Press.
- Rafaeli, A. (2013). Emotion in organizations: Considerations for family firms. *Entrepreneurship Research Journal*, 3(3), 295–300.
- Reedy, P. C., & King, D. R. (2017). Critical performativity in the field: Methodological principles for activist ethnographers. *Organizational Research Methods*.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/1094428117744881>
- Rhodes, C., Pullen, A., & Clegg, S. R. (2010). 'If I should fall from grace...': Stories of change and organizational ethics. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 91(4), 535–551.
- Ripamonti, S., Galuppo, L., Gorli, M., Scaratti, G., & Cunliffe, A. L. (2016). Pushing action research toward reflexive practice. *Journal of Management Inquiry*, 25(1), 55–68.
- Rosile, G. A., Boje, D. M., Carlon, D. M., Downs, A., & Saylor, R. (2013). Storytelling diamond: An antenarrative integration of the six facets of storytelling in organization research design. *Organizational Research Methods*, 16(4), 557–580.
- Samra-Fredericks, D. (2003). Strategizing as lived experience and strategists' everyday efforts to shape strategic direction. *Journal of Management Studies*, 40(1), 141–174.
- Sanchez, R. (2004). Understanding competence-based management: Identifying and managing five modes of competence. *Journal of Business Research*, 57(5), 518–532.
- Sanchez, R., Heene, A., & Thomas, H. (1996). Towards the theory and practice of competence-based competition. In R. Sanchez, A. Heene, & H. Thomas (Eds.), *Dynamics of competence-based competition: Theory and practice in the new strategic* (pp. 1–35). Pergamon.
- Sandberg, J., & Tsoukas, H. (2011). Grasping the logic of practice: Theorizing through practical rationality. *Academy of Management Review*, 36(2), 338–360.
- Schatzman, L., & Strauss, A. L. (1973). *Field research: Strategies for a natural sociology*. Prentice Hall.

- Simpson, B. (2009). Pragmatism, Mead and the practice turn. *Organization Studies*, 30(12), 1329–1347.
- Sminia, H. (2009). Process research in strategy formation: Theory, methodology and relevance. *International Journal of Management Reviews*, 11(1), 97–125.
- Snow, D. A., Morrill, C., & Anderson, L. (2003). Elaborating analytic ethnography: Linking fieldwork and theory. *Ethnography*, 4(2), 181–200. <https://doi.org/10.1177/14661381030042002>
- Sonenshein, S. (2010). We're changing or are we? Untangling the role of progressive, regressive, and stability narratives during strategic change implementation. *Academy of Management Journal*, 53(3), 477–512.
- Spradley, J. P. (1980). *Participant observation*. Holt, Rinehart, and Winston.
- Stake, R. E. (1995). *The art of case study research*. Sage.
- Stake, R. E., & Trumbull, D. J. (1982). Naturalistic generalizations. *Review Journal of Philosophy and Social Science*, 7(1), 1–12.
- Stablein, R., & Nord, W. (1985). Practical and emancipatory interests in organizational symbolism: A review and evaluation. *Journal of Management*, 11(2), 13–28.
- Sveningsson, S., & Alvesson, M. (2003). Managing managerial identities: Organizational fragmentation, discourse and identity struggle. *Human Relations*, 56(10), 1163–1193.
- Tatli, A., & Özbilgin, M. F. (2012). An emic approach to intersectional study of diversity at work: A Bourdieuan framing. *International Journal of Management Reviews*, 14(2), 180–200.
- Teece, D. J. (2007). Explicating dynamic capabilities: The nature and microfoundations of (sustainable) enterprise performance. *Strategic Management Journal*, 28(13), 1319–1350.
- Timmermans, S., & Tavory, I. (2012). Theory construction in qualitative research: From grounded theory to abductive analysis. *Sociological Theory*, 30(3), 167–186.
- Tsoukas, H. (2017). Don't simplify, complexify: From disjunctive to conjunctive theorizing in organization and management studies. *Journal of Management Studies*, 54(2), 132–153.
- Tsoukas, H. (1989). The validity of idiographic research explanations. *Academy of Management Review*, 14(4), 551–561.
- Turner, S. F., & Rindova, V. (2012). A balancing act: How organizations pursue consistency in routine functioning in the face of ongoing change. *Organization Science*, 23(1), 24–46.

- Van Maanen, J. (2011). Ethnography as work: Some rules of engagement. *Journal of Management Studies*, 48(1), 218–234.
- von Foerster, H. (2003). For Niklas Luhmann: “How recursive is communication?”. In H. von Foerster, *Understanding understanding* (pp. 305–323). Springer.
- von Mises, L. (1949). *Human action: A treatise on economics*. Foundation for Economic Education.
- Watson, T. J. (2011). Ethnography, reality and truth: The vital need for studies of “how things work” in organizations and management. *Journal of Management Studies*, 48(1), 202–217.
- Weick, K. E. (2009). *Making sense of the organization: The impermanent organization* (Vol. 2). John Wiley & Sons.
- Weick, K. E., Sutcliffe, K. M., & Obstfeld, D. (2005). Organizing and the process of sensemaking. *Organization Science*, 16(4), 409–421.
- Wenzel, M., & Koch, J. (2018). From entity to process: Toward more process-based theorizing in the field of organizational change. *Journal of Accounting & Organizational Change*, 14(1), 80–98.
- Whitford, J., & Zirpoli, F. (2014). Pragmatism, practice, and the boundaries of organization. *Organization Science*, 25(6), 1823–1839.
- Willmott, H. (1997). Management and organization studies as science? *Organization*, 4(3), 309–344.